

ODE-based models of signaling networks in autophagy

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Abstract

Aberrant metabolism and nutrient processing are hallmarks of cancer. Autophagy is a catabolic process, clearing macromolecules and providing metabolite intermediates for anabolism. Autophagy safeguards healthy cells from tumorigenesis while mobilizing metabolites promoting tumor growth. Autophagy is controlled by the mTOR signaling network in conjunction with AMPK and ULK1. This kinase triad features highly intertwined feedback and feedforward mechanisms, complicating predictions on nutrient and drug response. ODE-based models offer a deterministic approach frequently used for the exploration of signaling dynamics. Recent ODE models of the mTOR-AMPK-ULK1 network revealed non-linear behaviors, bistable switches, and oscillatory patterns, shedding light on the robustness and adaptability of autophagy control. We highlight emerging perspectives on AMPK in mTORC1-ULK1 crosstalk and mechanisms for integration into future models.

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Introduction

Ordinary differential equation (ODE)-based models constitute a deterministic approach for elucidating the

dynamic behavior of biological systems, commonly used to investigate signaling network dynamics [1–4]. Kinetic modeling of feedback regulation is rooted in the field of cybernetics, which developed control theory as a means to describe the dynamics and stability of feedback systems and applied the principles to the description of the human brain and man-machine interactions [5]. Since Otto Warburg established a link between tumorigenesis and dysregulated glycolysis [6], energy metabolism continues to be a focus in cancer research, and computational models on the control of glycolysis and energy metabolism have been developed for many decades [7]. Growing understanding of autophagy as an alternative pathway for the recycling and provision of metabolite intermediates as anabolic building blocks has initiated efforts towards models of autophagy [8]. This review covers the latest utilization of ODE models in metabolic signaling with a focus on the mechanistic target of rapamycin (mTOR) and autophagy, and perspectives for applications in the context of cancer and response to nutrients, drugs and environmental compounds.

Cancer metabolism is characterized by profound changes in cellular energy utilization and nutrient processing [9]. As the mTOR signaling network has a key role in the synchronization of cell metabolism with growth and proliferation [10], mTOR and its upstream cues are targeted in cancer therapy by a multitude of small compound inhibitors [11]. Effectors of these treatments include autophagy regulators that are highly intertwined with mTOR signaling [11]. In healthy cells, autophagy is a cell-protective homeostatic pathway that facilitates degradation and recycling of damaged cellular material such as protein aggregates and damaged organelles, thereby promoting cellular health and providing building blocks to sustain anabolic processes [12,13]. However, dysregulated mTOR signaling and autophagy allow cancer cells to bypass quality control mechanisms and maintain their growth in a nutrient-poor microenvironment [13–15]. For instance, autophagy - enhanced by mTOR inhibitors intended to limit cancer cell proliferation - can promote proliferation in the inner, poorly vascularized regions of pancreatic tumors [16]. To understand drug resistance and response, it is important to delineate the dynamic interplay of interventions with regulatory networks that control autophagy. In this review, we explore recent

efforts in developing dynamic computational models for the signaling network upstream of autophagy.

mTOR, AMPK, ULK1 and autophagy

The serine/threonine kinase mTOR is a prime regulator of cell metabolism [17,18]. mTOR operates in two distinct complexes (Figure 1), mTOR complex 1 (mTORC1) [19,20] and mTOR complex 2 (mTORC2) [21] that contain shared (mLST8, MLST8, MTOR associated protein, LST8 homolog; DEPTOR, DEP domain-containing mTOR-interacting protein) and complex-specific subunits (mTORC1: Raptor, RPTOR, regulatory-associated protein of mammalian target of rapamycin; PRAS40, AKT1S1, proline-rich AKT substrate 40 kDa; mTORC2: RICTOR, rapamycin-insensitive companion of mTOR; mSIN1, MAPKAP1, MAPK associated protein 1) (Figure 1). The complexes differ not only in structure but also regarding their upstream cues and downstream effectors [22] and, hence, in function. The FDA-approved immunosuppressant and anti-cancer agent rapamycin and its analogues (rapalogues) bind and allosterically inhibit mTORC1 [11]. mTORC2 is only indirectly inhibited upon long term exposure to rapalogues [23–25]. The mTOR complexes enhance energy-expensive, anabolic processes. For instance, mTORC1 phosphorylates substrates such as S6K (RPS6KB1, ribosomal protein S6 kinase B1), 4E-BP1 (EIF4EBP1, eukaryotic translation initiation factor 4E binding protein 1) and CAD (carbamoyl-phosphate synthetase 2, aspartate transcarbamylase, and dihydroorotase) to enhance protein and nucleotide biosynthesis [22]. Class I PI3Ks (phosphoinositide-3-kinases) and the AGC kinase AKT (AKT1, AKT serine/threonine kinase 1) transduce growth factor signals via the small GTPase RHEB (Ras homolog, mTORC1 binding) to mTORC1. Receptor tyrosine kinase activation by growth factors (e.g., insulin, IGF1, EGF) mediates plasma membrane recruitment of PI3Ks, which convert phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphate (PIP₂) to phosphatidylinositol-3,4,5-triphosphate (PIP₃), generating scaffolds for the recruitment of the AGC kinases PDK1 (PDK1, 3-phosphoinositide dependent protein kinase 1) and AKT (reviewed in Ref. [26]). PDK1 mediated phosphorylation at T308 activates AKT, which in turn phosphorylates and inhibits the TSC (Tuberous Sclerosis Complex) protein complex (reviewed in Refs. [27,28]). The TSC complex acts as a GTPase activating protein (GAP) towards RHEB and, consequently, RHEB de-repression results in mTORC1 activation [29–31]. mTORC1 inhibits PI3K via a well-described negative feedback mechanism that involves phosphorylation of IRS1 (insulin receptor substrate 1) by S6K [32,33] and of GRB10 (growth factor receptor bound protein 10) by mTORC1 itself [34–36]. More recently, another negative feedback from AKT to IRS2 (insulin receptor substrate 2) which bypasses mTORC1 has been reported [37]. Amino acids activate mTORC1 via lysosomal translocation to the Lamtor/Ragulator complex

(LAMTOR1–5, late endosomal/lysosomal adaptor, MAPK and MTOR activator 1–5), which is enabled by the Rag GTPase heterodimers (RagA/RagC and RagB/RagD) and the GATOR1 and 2 (GAP activity towards Rags) protein complexes [38]. Amino acid sensors upstream of the GATOR1/2 complexes include SESN2 (Sestrin-2) [39–42] and CASTOR (cytosolic arginine sensor for mTORC1) [43] that transduce leucine and arginine signals, and SAMTOR (SAM sensor upstream of mTORC1/BTM2, base methyltransferase of 25S rRNA 2 homolog) which senses the methionine-derived metabolite S-adenosyl-methionine (SAM) [44]. ARF1 (adenosine diphosphate ribosylation factor–1 GTPase) is required for glutamine sensing by mTORC1 [45]. mTORC2 activation by growth factors and amino acids is less well understood [28,46,47]. mTORC2 phosphorylates the AGC kinases AKT [48,49] and SGK1 (serum/glucocorticoid regulated kinase 1) [50], as well as PKCs (protein kinases C) [51] which control cell survival and motility, and glucose homeostasis. The most commonly used readout for mTORC2 activity is AKT phosphorylation at S473, which resides in a C-terminal hydrophobic motif and is required for full AKT activation [26,47]. AKT regulation is complex as phosphorylation events at T308 and S473 influence each other and AKT is targeted by many other kinases [26,47]. This complicates the interpretation of S473 phosphorylation in relation to mTORC2 activity. Although lysosomes are considered as the main sites of mTORC1 activity, it also resides at endosomal surfaces, as well as peroxisomes, mitochondria, endoplasmic reticulum (ER), Golgi, and the nucleus [52–59]. mTORC2 resides mainly at the plasma membrane and at the mitochondria-associated ER membranes, a subpopulation of endosomal vesicles, lysosomes, the perinucleus and the nucleus [47,60–63]. Interestingly, activation of both mTOR complexes is influenced by lysosomal positioning, whereby central clustering exerts an inhibitory effect [64]. The finding that mTORC2 and AKT are activated by peripheral lysosomes is in line with the plasma membrane being an important site of activation for both kinases.

While enhancing anabolic processes, mTORC1 simultaneously suppresses catabolic pathways, with autophagy being the most extensively studied among them. Macroautophagy (in the following referred to as autophagy) degrades macromolecules (proteins, carbohydrates and lipids) and mediates turnover of endosomes and organelles [65–68]. Double membrane structures, called isolation membranes, originate from the plasma membrane and intracellular compartments to form autophagosomes, which sequester cytoplasmic macromolecules and organelles via selective or non-selective routes [69]. After fusion with lysosomes – leading to the formation of autolysosomes – the autophagy substrates are degraded by the lysosomal enzymes. mTORC1 inhibits the early stages of autophagy by inhibiting the core enhancer of autophagy initiation

Figure 1

The mTOR network. mTOR operates via two multiprotein complexes, mTORC1 and mTORC2 both of which are activated by growth factors. mTORC1 enhances protein synthesis, by phosphorylating S6K and 4E-BP1, and inhibits autophagy through phosphorylation of ULK1. mTORC2 enhances survival, motility and glucose metabolism by phosphorylating the AGC kinases AKT, PKC, and SGK1. Growth factors induce membrane recruitment and activation of PI3Ks, which convert PIP₂ to PIP₃. The antagonist PTEN (phosphatase and tensin homolog) dephosphorylates PIP₃, yielding PIP₂. PIP₃ serves as a scaffold for the plasma membrane recruitment of the AGC kinases PDK1 and AKT. PDK1-mediated phosphorylation at T308 activates AKT, which phosphorylates and inhibits the TSC protein complex. The TSC complex acts as a GAP towards the small GTPase RHEB, whose de-repression activates mTORC1. mTORC1 inhibits PI3Ks via negative feedback loops, involving phosphorylation of IRS1 by S6K and of GRB10 by mTORC1. Another negative feedback from AKT to IRS2 bypasses mTORC1. Amino acids activate mTORC1 via lysosomal translocation to the Lamtor/Ragulator complex, which is enhanced by the RagA/RagC and RagB/RagD GTPase heterodimers and the GATOR1 and 2 protein complexes, downstream of the sensors SESN2 (leucine), CASTOR (arginine), SAMTOR (S-adenosyl-methionine, SAM) and ARF1 (glutamine). mTORC1 inhibits the early stages of autophagy by phosphorylating ULK1 at S638 and S758. ULK1 phosphorylates the autophagy initiation complex (ATG13, FIP200, ATG101) and mediates its translocation to the isolation membrane and autophagosome formation. ULK1 exerts negative feedback towards mTORC1 by phosphorylating Raptor at S792. mTORC1 phosphorylates and inhibits the transcription factors TFEB and TFE3 which enhance lysosome biogenesis, lipid metabolism, and autophagy. AMPK is activated under energy stress by a rise in the cellular AMP:ATP ratio, leading to direct binding of adenine nucleotides to the AMPK γ subunit. This promotes AMPK phosphorylation at T172 by LKB1, CAMKK2/ β and TAK1. Glucose starvation activates AMPK also by recruitment of LKB1 and the scaffold protein AXIN1 to the Lamtor complex, which enhances T172 phosphorylation of lysosomal AMPK. LKB1-AXIN1 recruitment is mediated by Aldolase when unbound to fructose-1,6-bisphosphate (FBP), and the lysosomal v-ATPase. AMPK phosphorylates Raptor at S722 and S792 and the TSC complex subunit TSC2 at T1271 and S1387, all contributing to inhibition of mTORC1. mTORC1 phosphorylates the AMPK α subunits at S345/7, inhibiting AMPK. AMPK induces autophagy by phosphorylating ULK1 at S317, S556 and S778. AMPK also represses mTORC1 mediated ULK1-S638 phosphorylation, further adding to ULK1 activation. ULK1 phosphorylates AMPK at S108 on the β 1 subunit, constituting a positive feedback loop that sensitizes AMPK to allosteric activation. AMPK converges with ULK1 on Raptor-S792, adding to the negative feedback towards mTORC1. AMPK also enhances autophagy by activating TFEB and TFE3. Details on the feedback and crosstalk among ULK1, AMPK and mTORC1 are depicted in Figure 2. red P, inhibitory phosphorylation; green P, activating phosphorylation; SLC, solute carrier protein; IR, insulin receptor; IGF1R, insulin like growth factor 1 receptor; arg, arginine; leu, leucine; met, methionine; glu, glutamine. All other abbreviations are defined in the text.

ULK1 (unc-51 like autophagy activating kinase 1) via phosphorylation at residues S638 and S758 [70–72]. The serine/threonine kinase ULK exists in five isoforms of which ULK1 and ULK2 show the highest similarity [68]. They phosphorylate several members of the autophagy initiation complex including ATG13 (autophagy related 13), FIP200 (RB1CC1, RB1 inducible coiled-coil 1), and ATG101 (autophagy related 101), facilitating its translocation to the isolation membrane at the ER [71,73]. ULK1 exerts negative feedback towards mTORC1 by phosphorylating Raptor at S792 [74], thus buffering its own repression by mTORC1. mTORC1 phosphorylates and inhibits further autophagy factors that mediate autophagosome elongation and maturation [22], as well as TFEB (transcription factor EB) and TFE3 (transcription factor binding to IGHM enhancer 3) which mediate lysosome biogenesis. Phosphorylation by mTORC1 inhibits TFEB and TFE3 by sequestering them in the cytosol [75–78]. De-repression of TFEB/TFE3 upon mTORC1 inactivation enables their nuclear translocation, and enhances lipid metabolism [79], lysosome biogenesis, and autophagy [80–84]. mTORC1 has been also implicated in nuclear export of TFEB [85], adding a further layer to mTORC1-dependent TFEB shuttling between cytoplasm and nucleus.

AMPK (adenosine 5'-monophosphate (AMP)-activated kinase) [86] is another evolutionary conserved autophagy regulator, signaling to many substrates involved in metabolism, including ULK1 and mTORC1. The AMPK complex consists of a catalytic α subunit and the two regulatory subunits β and γ . In mammals, two genes code for subunit α ($\alpha 1$ and $\alpha 2$), two genes for subunit β ($\beta 1$ and $\beta 2$), and three genes for subunit γ ($\gamma 1$, $\gamma 2$, and $\gamma 3$). The subunits form heterotrimeric complexes consisting of one α , β , and γ subunit each. When the cellular AMP:ATP ratio rises under energy stress, AMPK is activated by direct binding of adenine nucleotides to its γ subunit [86,87]. AMP binding promotes phosphorylation of subunit α at T172, which is targeted by LKB1 (STK11, serine/threonine kinase 11), CAMKK2/ β (calcium/calmodulin dependent protein kinase kinase 2) and TAK1 (transforming growth factor- β -activated kinase 1). Glucose starvation activates AMPK also in an AMP-independent manner, by lysosomal recruitment of LKB1 and the scaffold protein AXIN1 (axin-1) to the Lamtor complex, which enhances T172 phosphorylation of lysosomal AMPK [87]. LKB1-AXIN1 recruitment is mediated by Aldolase (ALDOA/B/C, aldolase, fructose-bisphosphate A/B/C) when unbound to fructose-1,6-bisphosphate (FBP), and the lysosomal v-ATPase (Vacuolar-type H⁺ -ATPases protein group). Whether or not the lysosomal recruitment of mTORC1 and AMPK to the Lamtor complex is mutually exclusive remains to be determined. Their proximity at lysosomes likely enables the intricate feedback interplay between them (Figure 2): AMPK phosphorylates Raptor at S722 and S792 [88] and the TSC complex subunit TSC2 at

T1271 and S1387 (residue numbers for human TSC2 long variant) [89], leading to inhibition of mTORC1. Conversely, mTORC1 phosphorylates the AMPK α subunits at S345/7, inhibiting AMPK as determined by reduced AMPK-T172 phosphorylation and lysosomal localization [90,91]. AMPK induces autophagy by phosphorylating ULK1 at S317 [70], S556 [92] and S778 [70,93]. AMPK also represses the mTORC1 mediated ULK1-S638 phosphorylation [72], further adding to ULK1 activation. Conversely, ULK1 phosphorylates AMPK at S108 on the $\beta 1$ subunit [94,95], constituting a positive feedback loop that sensitizes AMPK to allosteric activation [86]. There is also negative feedback from ULK1 to AMPK by phosphorylation of all three AMPK subunits on unknown sites, which prevents AMPK hyperactivation [96]. AMPK converges with ULK1 on Raptor-S792 [74,88], and thus AMPK and ULK1 likely synergize in exerting negative feedback towards mTORC1. In addition to ULK1, AMPK enhances autophagy by activating TFEB and TFE3, but it is unclear if this is mediated by direct phosphorylation of TFEB/TFE3 or indirectly by inhibition of mTORC1 [80,86]. A recent study postulated an inhibitory role of AMPK in autophagy by ULK1 phosphorylation at T660 [97]. Concomitant phosphorylation at ULK1-S556 and T660 increased AMPK-ULK1 binding resulting in ULK1 inactivation [97]. It will be interesting to investigate the interplay of this mechanism with AMPK-mediated ULK1 activation in the control of autophagy.

Mathematical modeling of the AMPK-mTOR-ULK1 triad in autophagy

Recent ODE-based dynamic models provide insight into the intricate regulatory loops between mTORC1, ULK1/2, and AMPK. They were designed to reveal regulatory patterns in autophagy during nutrient starvation versus nutrient-replete conditions and upon mTORC1, AMPK and ULK1 inhibition. Negative feedback loops at the level of kinase signaling establish robustness against fluctuating protein levels [98], which seems particularly relevant in the context of high protein turnover during autophagy. Furthermore, negative feedback can give rise not only to linear behavior but also elicits complex behavior such as adaptation or oscillations [99].

The multiple regulatory feedbacks in autophagy have been suggested to protect cells from excessive autophagy and contribute to metabolic homeostasis [100] by coordinating the utilization of building blocks - mobilized during autophagic phases - in the following biosynthesis phases. Driven by the notion that autophagy and protein synthesis are switching in a bistable manner, and covering ULK1 activation by AMPK, ULK1 inhibition by mTORC1, mutual inhibition between mTORC1 and ULK1, and negative feedback from ULK1 to AMPK, Szymańska et al. [101] constructed a literature-based model topology (Table 1, A). They

Figure 2

Feedback regulation in the AMPK-mTORC1-ULK1 kinase triad. AMPK activates ULK1 by phosphorylating S317 [70], S556 [92] and S778 [70,93], and mTORC1 inhibits ULK1 by phosphorylation at S638 and S758 [70,72]. mTORC1 also inhibits AMPK by phosphorylating its α 1 and α 2 subunits at S345/7 [90,91]. Both ULK1 and AMPK inhibit mTORC1 by phosphorylating Raptor-S792 [74,88]. AMPK phosphorylates Raptor at S722 [88] and TSC2 at T1271 and S1387 (residue numbers for human TSC2 long variant) [89], contributing to mTORC1 inhibition. AMPK represses the mTORC1 mediated ULK1-S638 phosphorylation [72], further adding to ULK1 activation. ULK1 phosphorylates AMPK at S108 on the β 1 subunit [94,95], constituting a positive feedback loop that sensitizes AMPK to allosteric activation [86]. There is evidence for negative feedback from ULK1 to AMPK by phosphorylation of all three AMPK subunits, yet the phosphorylation sites are unknown [96]. A recent study postulated an inhibitory role of AMPK in autophagy, with concomitant phosphorylation at ULK1-S556 and T660 increasing AMPK-ULK1 binding, resulting in ULK1 inactivation [97]. Abbreviations are defined in the text.

conducted rule-based modeling, with parameters of the ODEs based on theoretical considerations that were inspired by literature findings from different cell systems. The simulations suggested that bistable switching between ULK1-driven autophagy and mTORC1-driven translation is enabled by mutual inhibition between

mTORC1 and ULK1. Oscillations occurred only in the special case of slow negative feedback from ULK1 to AMPK, when AMPK activity in response to energy stress (AMP:ATP ratio) was set to intermediate levels [96]. In contrast, high energy stress corresponding to high levels of AMPK activity or rapamycin generated sustained

Table 1

ODE models simulating energy stress associated signaling dynamics of the AMPK-mTORC-ULK1 network. column 1, citation; column 2, network topology; column 3, simulation dynamics of AMPK, ULK1 and mTORC1 upon energy stress; column 4, mathematical terms required for AMPK dynamics; columns 5,6, parameterization & validation on experimental data.

	model topology	dynamic response to starvation perturbation	terms that mediate AMPK dynamics	parameterization on experimental data	experimental validation
2015 Szymańska et al. [101]		<p>AMPK activation</p>	<p>negative feedback from ULK1 to AMPK enables limit cycle oscillations.</p> <p>parameter p_6 (equation 10) set to 10^6</p>	no	no
2019 Holczner et al. [102]		<p>AMPK activation</p>	<p>negative feedback from mTORC1 to AMPK enables AMPK activation.</p>	no	time course data HEK293 cells
2020 Holczner et al. [106]		<p>AMPK activation</p>	<p>delayed negative feedback from ULK1 to AMPK, mediated by (1) or (2) enables limit cycle oscillations.</p> <p>(1) molecular element ProtX between AMPK and ULK1, represented through extra terms: kapr, kapr', kibr, jpr</p> <p>(2) sequential phosphorylation of AMPK target sites in ULK1: ULK1P, ULK1PP, ULK1PPP, ULK1PPPP</p>	no	time course data HEK293 cells
2021 Kapuy et al. [113]		<p>AMPK activation</p>	<p>model based on [106] with generalized terms, see C.</p>	no	no
2022 Sadrija et al. [132]		<p>energy stress</p>	<p>oscillation mediated by</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •rates of deactivation: $K_{pmTORC1by_pAMPK}$, $K_{pmTORC1_by_pULK1}$, $K_{pAMPK_by_pULK1}$, $K_{pAMPK_by_pmTORC1}$, $K_{pULK1_by_pmTORC1}$ •rate of activation: $K_{ULK1_by_pAMPK}$ 	model fitted to experimental data from [106]	no

(A) Negative feedback from ULK1 to AMPK (marked by *) enables oscillations upon intermediate AMPK activation. Simulation dynamics reproduced from [101, Figure 4B, D]. (B) Negative feedback from mTORC1 to AMPK (marked by *) enables the model to match observed pAMPK-T172 dynamics. Simulation dynamics reproduced from [102, Figure S2A]. HEK293, human embryonic kidney cells. (C) Delayed negative feedback from ULK1 to AMPK (marked by *) via molecular element ProtX or multi-site phosphorylation of ULK1 enables oscillations. Simulation dynamics reproduced from [106, Figure 6B]. variables: kapr: background activation of ProtX, kapr': AMPK-dependent activation of ProtX, kipr: background inactivation of ProtX, jpr: Michaelis-Menten-constant of ProtX; ULK1P, ULK1PP, ULK1PPP: inactive mono-, di-, tri-phosphorylated form of ULK1, ULK1PPPP: active fully-phosphorylated form of ULK1. (D) Generalized model that extends oscillatory behavior to ER stress, or oxidative stress and postulates AUIN (autophagy inducers), AUCCO (autophagy controllers), AUCCX (autophagy executors). Simulation dynamics reproduced from [113, Figure 2C]. (E) Model that contains feedback loops previously established (A-C) and investigates AMPK-dependent switching between mTORC1 and mTORC2. Simulation dynamics reproduced from [132, Figure 2A-C]. grey: model inputs, blue: model outputs, red asterisks: model elements that enable dynamic responses (shown as red lines).

autophagy activation without oscillation. The model was neither parameterized nor validated on experimental data, yet it provides a thorough analysis of non-linear dynamic behaviors that the network can show in principle. In a series of follow up studies, the Kapuy group drew on this model as a basis for dynamic data driven modeling of the mTOR-ULK1-AMPK interplay (Table 1, B-D). Comparing the model simulations with dynamic phosphorylation data from HEK293 cells, they noted that the model did not reproduce enhanced AMPK-T172 phosphorylation upon mTORC1 inhibition by rapamycin [102]. This led them to postulate a negative feedback loop from mTORC1 to AMPK (Table 1, B). Indeed, introduction of negative feedback from mTORC1 to AMPK reproduced AMPK activation by starvation or rapamycin in the model simulations. Negative feedback from mTORC1 to AMPK has been demonstrated earlier by ODE-based data driven modeling of dynamic phosphorylation data from insulin stimulated HeLa cells, upon mTORC1 inhibition by Raptor knockdown [103]. Negative feedback from mTORC1 to AMPK is also supported by other, experimental studies showing e.g., that AMPK is activated by ablation of mTORC1 [104] or S6K [105] in mice. The Petersen lab has recently reported the mechanism via which mTORC1 inhibits AMPK, namely through direct AMPK $\alpha 1$ S347 and $\alpha 2$ S345 phosphorylation by mTORC1 [90]. The studies highlight how model-based predictions could guide discoveries of new molecular mechanisms with biomedical relevance. As the studies did not cite each other, they also demonstrate the need for stronger networks between modeling and experimental labs in order to harness the full potential of systems modeling for biomedical research. Based on the discovery of negative feedback between mTORC1 and AMPK, the Kapuy lab developed a follow up model to address the concept of oscillations in the AMPK-mTORC1-ULK1 triad and autophagy [106]. They experimentally established that upon glucose stress or rapamycin-mediated mTORC1 inhibition, the network oscillates in 8 h and 2 h rhythms, respectively, and they observed a delay in initial AMPK-pT172 induction and subsequent phosphorylation of the AMPK target sites in ULK1, followed by a drop in AMPK-pT172 (Table 1, C). Therefore, they postulated a hysteresis effect, in that de-repression of AMPK upon mTORC1 inhibition is a fast event whereas subsequent ULK1 activation by AMPK is delayed, leading in turn to AMPK inhibition.

Two mechanisms were proposed to mediate this delay, (1) an additional molecular element between AMPK and ULK1 or (2) sequential phosphorylation of the multiple AMPK target sites in ULK1. Both alternatives were introduced into the model, and both models were able to reproduce oscillatory behavior in AMPK and ULK1 activity and autophagy. As multisite phosphorylation of ULK1 by AMPK is established [70,72,92,97], the second mechanism appears conceivable. There is also evidence for AMPK targets which have been linked with ULK1 regulation, including several phosphatases such as PP2A (PPP2CA: protein phosphatase 2 catalytic subunit alpha) and PP1A (PPP1CA: protein phosphatase 1 catalytic subunit alpha) [107,108]. Hence, both mechanisms may act in parallel and experimental validation is needed to establish their involvement and contribution to delayed feedback from ULK1 to AMPK. Auto-regulatory ULK1-dependent phosphorylation of phosphatase targets [109] and double positive feedback between ATG8 family proteins (LC3, MAP1LC, microtubule associated protein light chain/GABARAPs, GABA type A receptor associated proteins) and ULK1 [110] may further modulate this interplay.

Based on models of autophagy induction by nutrient (amino acid or carbohydrate), ER [111] and oxidative stress [112], the concept of multiple regulatory feedback mechanisms has been generalized in an ODE-based autophagy control network [113]. Based on their stress response dynamics, the autophagy control network classifies the regulatory elements into autophagy inducers, controllers, and executors (Table 1, D). mTORC1 is a separate element, making the autophagy control network specifically useful for the analysis of mTORC1-regulated autophagy. The autophagy control network model is based on the assumption that autophagy controllers such as ULK1 constitute key switches that control the on/off states of autophagy in reaction to cellular stress levels. The network contains the positive and negative feedback loops for the mTORC1-AMPK-ULK1 triad described above, whereby AMPK is classified as an autophagy inducer and ULK1 constitutes an autophagy controller. Exchange of nodes was introduced as an approach to classify molecules involved in autophagy based on their response dynamics to autophagy inducing stresses, and to adapt the autophagy control network model to a variety of stresses. For example, ULK1 could be exchanged for NRF2 (NF-E2-related

factor 2), a master regulator of the antioxidant response, or for CHOP (DDIT3, DNA damage inducible transcript 3) in order to adapt the model to ER stress conditions [112–115]. The models may constitute a valuable tool as a reference point for future studies that address complex behavior in autophagy networks.

Biphasic dependencies like those established for the mTORC1-AMPK-ULK1 triad also result when modeling PI3K/mTOR signaling investigating the mTORC1/2 shared subunit mLST8 together with (de) ubiquitylation by the E3 ligase TRAF2 and the deubiquitinase OTUD7B [116,117]. Ubiquitylation was implemented as a switch shifting mLST8 from mTORC2 into mTORC1 (model topology illustrated in Table 2, A). The ODE model was calibrated on

semiquantitative phosphorylation time course data upon insulin stimulation to study alternative model topologies at the level of IRS1/2 and mLST8 [117]. The simulations suggested a biphasic dependence of mTORC1 activity on the levels of the mTORC2 subunit mSIN1, and control of this mechanism by the TRAF2/OTUD7B-mLST8 axis. The prediction was experimentally tested in mSIN1^{-/-} mouse embryonic fibroblasts (MEFs), in which low mSIN1 re-expression increased S6K-pT389, whereas high mSIN1 re-expression inhibited S6K-pT389, while the mTORC2 readout AKT-pS473 increased monotonically with mSIN1 levels. Based on this, mTORC2 was postulated to act upstream of mTORC1, which contrasts with several studies showing that mTORC2 inhibition does not affect mTORC1 activity [118,119]. As mSIN1 has

Table 2

ODE models simulating nutrient-induced signaling dynamics of the PI3K/mTOR and AMPK-mTOR-SIRT1 networks. column 1, citation; column 2, network topology; column 3, key simulation dynamics upon nutrient signals; columns 4,5, parameterization & validation on experimental data.

	model topology	dynamic response to stimulation perturbation	parameterization on experimental data	experimental validation
2021 Ghomlaghi et al. [116]		<p>dose-response to increasing SIN1 or TRAF2 (model 4)</p>	<p>model fitted to MEF experimental data from [117]</p>	<p>time course in MEF WT & TRAF2^{-/-} cells [from ref 117], biphasic dependency of mTORC1 on SIN1 levels in MEF SIN1^{-/-} cells [116], single time point in C2C12 WT & C2C12 siIRS1/2 cells [116] <i>in silico</i> model customization for 342 cancer cell lines</p>
2021 Sadria et al. [125]		<p>protein depletion/repletion</p>	<p>model parameters taken from [123, 126-128] and fitted to experimental data from several cell lines [123, 127, 129, 130]</p>	<p>no</p>

(A) Model topology for ubiquitination-dependent mTORC1/mTORC2 regulation. Only the topology of model 4 yields simulations which fit experimental data. Model 4 supports an insulin receptor substrate-dependent biphasic MLST8 switch between mTORC1 and mTORC2. Simulation dynamics reproduced from [116, Figure 4A]. MEF, mouse embryonic fibroblasts. (B) Model topology for amino acid inputs into the mTORC1/mTORC2 signaling network. Shown is the simulated response to amino acid depletion (x<120min) and restoration (x>120min). Simulation dynamics reproduced from [125, Figure 4]. grey: model inputs, blue: model outputs.

mTORC2-independent functions at the level of RAS [120], an alternative explanation for the biphasic S6K-pT389 response to mSIN1 levels may be that low mSIN1 levels activate RAS towards the PI3K-mTORC1 axis, and high mSIN1 levels promote mTOR recruitment into mTORC2 thereby disassembling mTORC1. Nonetheless, the biphasic S6K-pT389 response to mSIN1 levels is interesting and potentially relevant. It was supported by simulations based on protein levels for 342 cell lines in the cancer cell line encyclopedia (CCLE, [121]), although the effect was not validated regarding S6K phosphorylation. Thus, the postulated relevance in the context of breast cancer remains a topic for future investigations. Another study on neuronal insulin/calcium signaling and energy consumption [122] also predicted multi-stable or oscillatory behavior involving AMPK-mTORC1/2 signaling, however with a scope other than cancer.

Investigating the interplay of the two mTOR complexes with nutrients and insulin by ODE-based modeling [103,123], semiquantitative time-course data from C2C12 myocytes suggested amino acid inputs not only to mTORC1 but also to PI3K, mTORC2 and AMPK [123]. In the light of lysosomal AMPK activation by glucose starvation, it is interesting to consider that insulin signals and amino acid stress may also be integrated by AXIN1 at the lysosomes [87,124]. We have shown that upon activation by amino acid re-addition, AMPK phosphorylates ULK1 and sustains autophagy under nutrient replete conditions [123]. This provides an alternative mechanism to the oscillatory autophagy switches suggested by other models [101,106,116,117]. The two scenarios may represent different physiological situations whereby switch-like events, giving rise to oscillatory autophagy behavior, occur under conditions such as long-term nutrient stress or inhibition of mTOR, AMPK, ULK1 or PI3K. Under nutrient replete conditions, concomitant activity of AMPK-driven autophagy and mTORC1-dependent biosynthetic processes may ensure a homeostatic supply of metabolite intermediates as building blocks for biosynthesis [12,13]. The recently postulated inhibitory action of AMPK towards ULK1 [97] seems to challenge the conventional view of AMPK as an inducer of autophagy. Accommodating this mechanism in dynamic ODE models may enable hypothesis building on the contribution of ULK1 inhibition by AMPK to oscillatory behavior and/or autophagy under nutrient replete conditions.

Another ODE-based model on amino acid signaling to the AMPK-mTOR network investigated the dynamics of the leucine sensor SESN2 via the GATOR complexes in relation to AKT, PRAS40 (AKT1S1), mTORC1, AMPK, NAD⁺ (nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide), and SIRT1 [125] (model topology illustrated in Table 2, B). The model parameters were taken from literature [123,126–128] and fitted to

published experimental data [123,127,129,130]. The model depicts a dual role of SESN2 in inhibiting mTORC1-S6K1 signaling while activating the AMPK-ULK1 axis [131]. A further ODE model encompassing AMPK, mTORC1 and mTORC2 was built to study the dual role of AMPK as a cancer suppressor in healthy cells or as a cancer promotor in the tumor context (Table 1, E) [132]. The study postulated insulin levels as a discriminator between beneficial or detrimental outcome of AMPK in cancer, and suggested concomitant mTORC2 inhibition and AMPK activation as a strategy to limit tumor cell growth. Both models harbor topological features that are not supported by experimental data, such as mTORC2 as an upstream activator of mTORC1 (discussed above and reviewed by Heberle et al. [28]). They were parameterized on literature data from a variety of cell systems from different organisms and organs, whose consistency and cancer relevance are unclear. The size of the network and number of parameters call for an identifiability analysis, yet model predictions recapitulate prior knowledge from literature. Hence, the models may constitute sources of modules for future in depth modeling studies. Another resource to model the mTORC1-mTORC2 network in cancer is offered by a recent study focusing on ER positive breast cancer [133]. The model comprehensively covers the interplay of the mTOR and MAP kinase networks with the estrogen receptor and contains several possible connection points with autophagy models including mTOR, ULK1, and AMPK. Hence, a model which allows to simulate autophagy in relation to cancer therapies targeting the PI3K-AKT-mTORC1 axis is within reach.

Discussion

In this review, we discuss recent advances in ODE-based mathematical modeling of autophagy control via the AMPK-mTOR-ULK1 signaling triad. Several models predicted that autophagy and protein synthesis oscillate in shifted phases [101,106,116,117]. Oscillation was suggested to be controlled by mutual inhibition of mTORC1 and ULK1, time-delayed feedback loops from ULK1 to AMPK, and a double negative feedback loop from AMPK to mTORC1. The mTORC2 component mSIN1 was shown to induce a biphasic response in S6K phosphorylation, suggesting that not only AKT but also mSIN1 may act at several nodes in the mTOR network. The experimental validation of some of the predicted regulatory connectivities highlights mathematical modeling as a valuable tool for hypothesis generation in oncogenic signaling. The model predictions call for an openness to non-canonical functions of known network components in oncogenic networks. However, the reliability of model-based predictions is proportional to the quality and solidity of the parameterization and validation data, which involves a thorough design of biological controls. For instance, knockout or

knockdown experiments need to be monitored in each replicate by quantification of the targeted proteins [102]. Furthermore, consistent readouts should be used across time courses for a given phenotype [106], or if not, a switch in readouts needs to be justified.

Current modeling approaches to AMPK signaling focus on adenine nucleotide sensing and phosphorylation by LKB1, CAMKK2/ β , and TAK1 [86] as well-established activating inputs to AMPK. In recent years, lysosome-recruitment of the AXIN1-LKB1 complex has turned out to be another important aspect of AMPK activation [87], but this mechanism has to the best of our knowledge not yet been covered by systems modeling. Model-based approaches will allow to consider AMPK sub-pools by separation into distinct parameter sets. This may help to assess for instance a possible competition of mTORC1 and LKB1-AXIN1 for Lamtor complex binding, or the role of the lysosomal compartment and its positioning in mediating feedback between mTORC1 and AMPK. Several modeling studies have addressed AMPK activity in the context of insulin signaling, which seems counter intuitive, as AMPK is typically considered to be activated by energy stress and nutrient shortage. As the model predictions are supported by a number of experimental studies, it seems promising to build models dissecting mTOR-AMPK crosstalk in response to single and combined nutrient inputs, such as glucose and distinct amino acids. Modeling of different AMPK sub pools may also help explain why in some metabolic contexts AMPK acts as a tumor suppressor and in others as a tumor promoter. Such insights may reveal novel mechanisms and the models may support the exploration of their suitability as markers and/or drug targets in cancer. It will also be intriguing to see whether and how common signaling or regulatory mechanisms are translatable between different molecular entities as suggested by Kapuy et al. [113]. The generalization of circuits in biological model systems will help to describe recurring patterns and save time in constructing signaling modules with similar regulation patterns. For instance, the integration of TFEB/TFE3 into autophagy models would be a logical next step that may help unravel whether AMPK is a direct or an indirect regulator of TFEB/TFE3. Such insight will help answer the question whether AMPK directly targets TFEB/TFE3 or indirectly via inhibition of mTORC1 [86,134–136].

Beyond signaling, mathematical models in autophagy have addressed vesicle dynamics, flux analysis, as well as spatial considerations [137,138]. Vesicle dynamics studies investigate the formation, transport, and fusion of autophagosomes and lysosomes [139]. For instance, flux analysis quantifies the rates of autophagic flux, defined as the process through which materials are sequestered, transported, and degraded within the autophagic pathway [68,140]. Combining such approaches with signaling models in autophagy will help

address the interplay between the rate of autophagic flux and different nutrient conditions and signals, and questions as complex as the influence of vesicle dynamics on drug response in cancer [137,138].

An inherent issue with any modelling approach is the degree of simplification and assumptions, which cannot fully capture the complexity of biological systems, calling for larger models that include more nodes, edges, and parameters. However, the model size is limited by the amount of data which is available for parameterization. In the models discussed here, two modes of model parameterization were realized, (1) by assigning values to the parameters within orders of magnitude deemed to be reasonable based on literature and the type of reaction, and validation of the model output against experimental data [102,106]; or (2) by parameter estimation based on experimental dynamic time course data [125,132]. For both approaches, scarce data are an issue: reaction rates are rarely measured in cell signaling research and, therefore, are typically not available for direct model parameterization; and parameter estimation relies on dynamic (time course) data whose density is sufficient to achieve at least partial parameter identifiability. Apart from identifiability issues, also the computational expense for parameter estimation increases with network size and limits the number of parameters that can be included while conducting the parameter search within a reasonable timeframe. Ideally, a model should be parameterized and validated on independent and compatible dynamic data sets, but this was only realized in one of the models discussed here [116]. None of the models performed identifiability analyses and hence it is unclear whether and which parts of the models are sufficiently constrained by experimental data. Multi-scale omics data permit the creation of extensive holistic maps. These static networks typically omit the dynamic nature of biological systems, but models that integrate dynamic multi-omics data are currently being developed [141–143] raising exciting perspectives for novel insights into regulatory circuits in oncogenic signaling, metabolism, autophagy and beyond.

The models discussed here all simulate signaling upstream of autophagy at time scales from minutes to hours, while drug response in cancer therapy happens in the range of days to months. The predictive relevance of short time-scale models on autophagy for cancer therapy remains to be shown. Results from other signaling network models e.g., on the EGFR-MAPK network [144], are encouraging as drug-induced changes in short term network dynamics correspond to long term phenotypic changes in cell growth. Apart from the well-studied nutrient and energy inputs to the mTOR-AMPK-ULK1 triad, metabolic disruption by environmental compounds is understudied, yet it is highly relevant to autophagy control [145,146] and drug response [147]. Modeling these disruptions is likely to

synergize with established physiologically based kinetic (PBK) modeling in toxicology. The number, scope and findings of the available models on autophagy signaling highlight both the promise and the need to target the topic by the wider systems oncology community, to link the models with clinical and environmental data, and render the complexity of autophagy control dynamics amenable to drug targeting in distinct tumor entities and metabolic states.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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- * of special interest
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